

CoARA-UIB Action Plan 2026-2027

Action plan of the University of the Balearic Islands for the reform of research evaluation, approved by the Governing Council in session dated 17 of June of 2026.

Background

The university is, by definition, an institution dedicated to the creation, transmission and transfer of knowledge at the service of society. Evaluation and accountability are essential tools for analysis and improvement, which allows performance to be assessed in the context of missions, values, principles and objectives. In order to fulfil the mission entrusted to it with guarantees of quality and responsibility, the university recognises the evaluation of research and innovation as a central element of its activity. The processes, methodologies and evaluation criteria condition the recruitment and promotion of talent and guide the mechanisms for recognising and stimulating research and innovation. Consequently, the guiding principles of the evaluation of research and innovation must be formulated with full awareness and rigour, in coherence with the missions, values and principles of the UIB, and must allow the diversity of contributions and impacts that the institution and society consider relevant to be assessed.

In this regard, the University of the Balearic Islands (UIB), committed to standards of academic excellence and aware of the need for a reform of the assessment of research and innovative activity, signed the Agreement [on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (ARRA) in November 2022 and in May 2024 the [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment](#) (DORA). The ARRA, published in July 2022 and promoted by the European Commission, the *European University Association (EUA)* and Science Europe, establishes ten principles to reform evaluation criteria and processes, respecting the autonomy of the organizations involved. These principles are embodied in four fundamental commitments:

1. To recognise the diversity of contributions and trajectories in research in accordance with the needs and nature of each discipline.
2. Base the evaluation mainly on qualitative criteria, in which peer review is central, supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. Abandon the uncritical, decontextualized and reductionist use of metrics based on journals and publications.

4. Avoid the use of rankings that evaluate research organizations as a scientific evaluation criterion.

Six support commitments are added:

5. Commit the necessary resources to reform research evaluation and achieve committed organizational changes.
6. Review and develop criteria, tools and processes for evaluating research in collaboration with stakeholders.
7. Raise awareness about the reform of research evaluation and provide transparent communication, guidance and training on the new criteria and processes, as well as on their use.
8. Exchange practices and experiences with other institutions to promote mutual learning.
9. Communicate the progress made in the implementation of the commitments, facilitating self-assessment and collective monitoring.
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, ensuring that the data used are available in open access to the research community.

With the aim of effectively implementing ARRA, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) *was established in December 2022*, to which the UIB joined as a constituent member. CoARA, which brings together universities, research centres, public administrations, quality assurance agencies and scientific societies, is a platform for experimentation and the development of new criteria and tools for the evaluation of research and the exchange of good practices. On 18 July 2023, the proposal for the creation of the Spanish Chapter of CoARA (SNC) was approved, presented by the Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities (CRUE), the National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (ANECA) and the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The Chapter's objectives are to plan the reform of research evaluation in Spain until 2030, to co-design possible evaluation systems with the contribution of the institutions and organizations that make up the Spanish research and innovation ecosystem, to test the results of this reform through pilot projects, and to apply the reform in a gradual and coordinated manner to minimize negative impacts. In September 2025, the SNC published its report *Mapping Institutional Approaches to Research Assessment Reform: Insights from the CoARA Spanish National Chapter*, which collects emerging institutional practices

in research assessment reform in Spain, identifies shared trends and common challenges, and provides a solid empirical basis for the design of recommendations and future actions.

The commitment to the reform of the research evaluation system is also reflected in recent state regulations, such as [Royal Decree 678/2023](#), which introduces modifications to the accreditation of teachers and researchers aligned with the principles of ARRA and establishes specific criteria for incorporating open science practices into the evaluations of quality control agencies. Likewise, the [National Strategy for Open Science](#) (ENCA) 2023-2027 provides for new systems for evaluating scientific performance with incentives and recognitions that promote open access to results, data, protocols and methodologies, and promote citizen science. One of the main effects of these changes can be seen in the modification of the [evaluation criteria for six-year terms and ANECA's accreditations](#), which promote the responsible combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators, together with a narrative presentation of the merits.

By signing the ARRA, the UIB undertook to draw up an institutional Action Plan to review the internal research evaluation system and incorporate, in a progressive and structured way, its principles and new practices that emphasize quality, diversity, inclusion, equity and transparency, while guaranteeing adequate information to the university community. This plan includes the initiatives promoted to implement the Agreement for the Reform of Research Assessment, as well as the actions planned for the period 2026-2027, with annual monitoring and continuous improvement mechanisms. It is a living document, subject to revision and updating according to internal learning, the available evidence and the evolution of the national and European framework.

Background aligned with the CoARA principles

At the time of presentation of this Action Plan, the UIB has several initiatives and practices aligned with the principles and objectives of CoARA:

- It signs the *Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment* (ARRA) and joins the *Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment* (CoARA).
- Adherence to the [European Charter for Research Staff and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Research Staff](#) (C&C).

- Integration into [the Human Resources Strategy for Research Staff](#) (HRS4R) and obtaining the [HR Excellence in Research seal](#).
- Approval of Regulatory [Agreement 14540/2022](#), of 15 June, which regulates the recruitment of research staff, as well as technical or research management staff, in accordance with the principles of the C&C and the recruitment policy based on open, transparent and merit-based criteria (OTM-R, *Open, Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment of Researchers*).
- Approval of [Regulatory Agreement 14934/2023](#), of 4 May, which establishes the criteria for hiring teaching and research staff in the modalities of assistant professor and associate professor.
- The [Research Evaluation Committee of the Research Area](#) (CARAI) evaluates applications for research grant and promotion programmes managed by the Office of the Vice-Rector for Scientific Policy and Research in accordance with the principles of the C&C and the HRS4R guidelines.
- Signing of the San Francisco Declaration [on Research Assessment](#) (DORA) *in May 2024*.
- Adhesion to the [Barcelona Declaration for Open Research Information](#).
- Approval of the [UIB Strategic Plan for the period 2023-2027](#), which includes specific objectives such as promoting integrity and ethics in research (R02), promoting the transition to the open research paradigm (R07) and evaluating research based on quality criteria through multidimensional excellence accreditation mechanisms (R09).
- The UIB has begun to promote new approaches to research evaluation. Thus, for the ["Santander Scholarships - Postdoctoral Research" Programme for short stays of young doctors in international research centres of recognised prestige](#), the Office of the Vice-Rector for Scientific Policy and Research has established evaluation criteria aligned with the principles of CoARA, avoiding the exclusive use of quantitative bibliometric parameters.
- Promotion of interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research through the creation and recognition of various types of R+D+I structures, through:
 - Regulatory [Agreement 12843/2018](#), of 24 July, approving the regulations governing university research institutes of the UIB;
 - Regulatory Agreement 15350/2024, of 21 February, modified by AN15769/2025, which regulates the organisational structures for research, innovation and transfer at the UIB. In addition, it is planned

to establish a scale for the evaluation of structures that, given their transversality and multidisciplinary nature, takes into account the evaluation guidelines issued by CoARA.

- Realization of the [I Open Science Conference at the UIB: Promoting responsible, transparent and collaborative research](#).
- Completion of several training courses on the new paradigms of research: [Starting research](#), [Towards open science](#), [Open data management](#) and [Scientific dissemination](#).
- The UIB is part of the [EUNICoast](#) alliance, the European University of Islands, Ports and Coastal Territories, which aims to promote a collaborative research model, committed to sustainability and responding to the social and environmental challenges of island and coastal communities. The research practices are impact-oriented and aligned with the principles of CoARA, integrating social and environmental indicators, and promoting open science as well as technology transfer with local actors.

These actions constitute the first advances at the UIB towards the responsible transformation of internal research evaluation mechanisms, while consolidating a model of excellence aligned with European policies and the values of social commitment and scientific integrity.

Objectives

The UIB's membership of CoARA is part of the strategic objective of promoting a responsible and planned transformation in the evaluation processes of research and innovation, professional trajectories and the social impact of knowledge. This Action Plan transfers the commitments of the [Agreement for the Reform of Research Assessment](#) to the institutional context of the UIB and aligns them with the [Strategic Plan 2023-2027](#), with the guidelines of HRS4R and OTM-R to guarantee coherence between the evaluation criteria and the human resources selection processes, with the internal quality instruments established in different regulations, calls and procedures, with the evaluation criteria for six-year periods and accreditations adopted by the National Commission for the Evaluation of Research Activity (CNEAI) and by the quality assurance agencies, as well as with the principles of open science. This alignment seeks coherence, efficiency and sustainability over time.

The Plan aims to establish a common framework for a new culture of research evaluation, based on the responsible use of bibliometric indicators and qualitative assessment, which allows progress towards more transparent processes that recognise the diversity of scientific activity; deploy an operational programme of actions with responsibilities, deadlines and indicators; and provide the institution with a stable mechanism for monitoring, learning and accountability. Specifically, the Plan pursues the following operational objectives:

- Align the institutional strategy of research, transfer and innovation with the principles and commitments of CoARA.
- To participate institutionally in the reform of research evaluation at national and European level, and to inform the university community of its development.
- Review and adapt the criteria, processes and tools for the internal evaluation of people, structures and projects, guaranteeing equity between all areas of knowledge.
- Develop, pilot and implement alternative or complementary assessment practices, based on expert judgment and qualitative evidence, with responsible, critical and conscious use of bibliometric indicators, and promote the use of narrative curricula that reflect the complete career of research staff.
- Strengthen the assessment of open science initiatives (transparency and accessibility of results) and the diversity of contributions (data, software, protocols, mentoring, transfer, social impact).
- To promote the recognition of diverse trajectories and different stages.
- To guarantee legal certainty through clear, transparent and fair rules that give certainty to researchers and to the evaluation and selection committees.
- Share information openly and proactively, involving groups in the design, implementation and monitoring of the reform.
- To consolidate the culture of responsible assessment throughout the university community and to train research staff in the central aspects.

The Plan covers the period 2026-2027 and its implementation will be subject to annual evaluation and review, with evidence-based adjustments. Each year, the CoARA-UIB Working Group will prepare a follow-up report that will be presented to the Research Committee and the Governing Council, and which will be published on

the institutional website. At the end of 2027, a final evaluation of the Plan will be carried out, which will serve as the basis for the design of the next cycle (2028-2030).

Scope and implementation of the Plan

A large part of the evaluations in which UIB research staff participate are promoted by external bodies and agencies (public talent recruitment and retention programmes, competitive calls for research projects, transfer and dissemination at regional, state and European level, six-year periods and accreditations). Consequently, a significant part of these processes exceeds the scope of the Plan. The scope of application is limited, without prejudice to other provisions in force, to:

- i) calls for applications for the [Programme for the Promotion of Research and Innovation](#) managed by the Office of the Vice-Principal for Scientific Policy and Research, with the support of the Research Area, which require the evaluation of the activity of the R+D+I structures or the individualised trajectory of researchers;
- ii) calls for contracts funded under Chapter I of the UIB budget for research, technical or research management staff;
- iii) calls for contracts funded under Chapter VI of the UIB budget for research, technical or research management staff;
- iv) internal processes for selecting or prioritising candidates for external calls in which the institution has a limited number of applications allowed.

In calls for teaching and research staff under Chapter I in which the assessment of research activity is relevant, the reforms provided for in this Plan will be applied to the criteria and procedures of the corresponding committees, in coordination with the competent Vice-Rector's Office and with full respect for the applicable regulatory framework.

The proposed changes will be specified through the adaptation of regulations, calls, committee guides and management tools. Therefore, the implementation will follow a gradual approach – pilot tests, evaluation and scaling – with the involvement of the university community to minimize the administrative burden, guarantee equity between disciplines and avoid negative impacts on ongoing trajectories. It will be governed by principles of participation, proportionality and transparency, avoiding uniform solutions and ensuring co-creation with the

community, accountability and publicity through a specific website, annual reports and, where possible, open data, in coherence with regulations and available institutional resources.

Identified risks and mitigation measures

The implementation of the Plan addresses known risks that must be anticipated:

Misalignment with criteria of external agencies (ANECA, CNEAI, regional agencies): the state and European framework will be continuously monitored and internal criteria will be adjusted when necessary to avoid damage to individual trajectories.

Additional administrative burden on evaluation committees and research staff: priority will be given to the use of shared tools and templates, prior training and the staggered introduction of changes.

Inequalities between areas of knowledge in the application of the new criteria: the institutional guide will include lists of evidence differentiated by area and the commissions will have contextualized criteria.

Resistance to cultural change: the internal communication plan and the training activities will be specifically aimed at this dimension.

Resource constraints: the Working Group will annually review the feasibility of the actions and prioritise them according to impact and budget availability.

CoARA-UIB Working Group

In 2022, the Research Committee created the Open Science Working Group, which is working on the elaboration of the UIB Open Science Plan as a reference framework for the promotion, implementation and consolidation of practices that foster transparency, open access to knowledge, the reuse of results, citizen participation and accountability.

With the approval of this Plan, the CoARA-UIB Working Group is constituted, made up of:

- the Vice-Rector for Scientific Policy and Research, who is responsible for the management of
- the Vice-Rector for Strategic Planning, Equality and Communication
- the Vice-Rector for Teaching and Research Staff
- the Vice-Principal for Innovation and Digital Transformation
- the Vice-Rector for International Relations, Solidarity and Global Justice
- representatives of the Research Committee who cover different areas of knowledge and are at different stages of their research career
- the president of the Research Ethics Committee
- the management team of the Research Area, which is responsible for the technical secretariat, which will provide operational support and ensure the traceability of decisions
- the director of the Office of Strategic Planning
- the director of the Office for Knowledge Transfer
- the director of the Management and Support Unit for Teaching and Research Staff
- the director of the Doctoral School
- the head of the Library Service
- the head of the Research Services Unit of the Library, Documentation and Archive Area

The main objective of this group is to coordinate the implementation, governance and monitoring, with periodic accountability and annual evidence-based reviews of this CoARA-UIB Action Plan 2026-2027. To this end, its functions are:

- Review and propose improvements to the CoARA-UIB Action Plan.
- Plan, prioritise and promote actions, and coordinate their execution.
- To collect and channel proposals for improvement from the university community.
- To identify areas of application of the CoARA principles at the UIB.
- To generate a space for debate and reflection on methodologies and indicators for the evaluation of academic careers and the social impact of research, promoting expert judgment, the narrative curriculum and the responsible use of indicators.
- Evaluate the feasibility of the proposals and define implementation procedures (regulations, calls, committee guides and management tools), in coordination with the corresponding responsible units.

- Monitor implementation and results, promoting the necessary changes as a result of the detection of opportunities for improvement, and inform the university community about them.
- To promote, plan and coordinate the carrying out of specific training activities on reforms, aimed at research staff and evaluation and selection committees.

The group will meet at least three times a year and will present an annual report to the UIB's governing bodies that includes the actions promoted, the state of implementation and, where appropriate, proposals for improvement.

The Working Group will ensure that the development of the principles and commitments of CoARA at the UIB are integrated into the institutional Strategic Plan and the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R). The participation of the Office of the Vice-Principal for Strategic Planning, Equality and Communication guarantees the coordination of aspects related to equality, gender and other intersectionalities. Likewise, the participation of the Office of the Vice-Principal for International Relations, Solidarity and Global Justice promotes the inclusion of the social responsibility dimension in the proposed actions:

CoARA-UIB Action Plan

ARRA Commitments	Lines of action	& Actions	Calendar	Responsible	Agents involved	Evaluation mechanisms
<p>1. To recognise the diversity of contributions and trajectories in research in accordance with the needs and nature of each discipline.</p> <p>2. Base the evaluation mainly on qualitative criteria, in which peer review is central, supported by the responsible use of quantitative indicators.</p> <p>3. Abandon the inappropriate use of metrics based on journals and publications.</p> <p>4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations as a criterion for scientific evaluation.</p>	Institutional commitment to the reform of research evaluation promoted by CoARA.	Institutional declaration aligned with the principles and commitments of CoARA, which incorporates the institutional organization necessary to advance in the reform of research evaluation.	2Q 2026	VR Science Policy and Research.	Commission of Inquiry. Board of Directors. Governing Council.	Institutional declaration approved by the Research Committee, the Board of Directors and the Governing Council, published and disseminated.
5. Commit the necessary resources to reform research evaluation and	Governance and resources to guarantee the viability	Create the CoARA-UIB Working Group.	2Q 2026	VR Science Policy and Research.	Board of Directors.	Agreement of the Board of Directors.

achieve committed organizational changes.	of the CoARA-UIB Action Plan.	Assign an annual budget for the implementation of the actions envisaged in the CoARA-UIB Action Plan (technical and logistical support, training and communication).	2026-2027	VR Science Policy and Research.	Board of Directors.	Agreement of the Board of Directors.
	Planning, implementation and monitoring of the CoARA-UIB Action Plan.	To prepare and approve the CoARA-UIB Action Plan.	2Q 2026	VR Science Policy and Research.	CoARA-UIB Working Group.	CoARA-UIB Action Plan approved by the Research Committee, the Board of Directors and the Governing Council. Presentation of the Plan to the university community.
		Implementation, development and monitoring of the Plan.	2026-2027	Directorate of the Research Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group.	Minutes of meetings, at least every six months. Annual monitoring report.
6. Review and develop criteria, tools and processes for evaluating research in collaboration with stakeholders.	Review, analysis and updating of internal calls to incorporate criteria aligned with the principles of CoARA.	Mapping of the calls, tools and mechanisms in force at the UIB that involve the evaluation of the research activity of people or R+D+I structures.	3Q 2026	Directorate of the Research Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group.	Diagnosis report.
		Develop an institutional guide for the responsible and transparent evaluation of research (people, R+D+I structures and projects) based on the CoARA principles	2026-2027	Directorate of the Research Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Commission of Inquiry.	Minutes of meetings with the university community to explore and suggest new avenues for research evaluation.

		(interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research, narrative CV, balanced use of qualitative indicators and assessments, social impact and transfer, open science, diversity of contributions and lists of evidence by areas of knowledge).				Publication of the guide. Presentation of the guide to the university community.
		Pilot test of the application of the institutional guide for the responsible and transparent evaluation of research in a call (for example, mobility grants or the promotion of predoctoral training) and evaluation of its effect.	1Q 2027	Directorate of the Research Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Research Evaluation Committee of the Research Area. Office of Management of the Programme for the Development and Human Resources for Research.	Evaluation report of the pilot test. Minutes of the evaluation committee. Satisfaction surveys of committee members and candidates.
		To review and update, where appropriate, the terms and conditions of the calls of the Programme for the Promotion of Research and Innovation that involve the evaluation of research activity, with the aim of progressively incorporating the CoARA principles.	2026-2027	Directorate of the Research Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Commission of Inquiry.	Percentage of calls adapted to the CoARA principles.

		To review and update, where appropriate, the regulations governing the recruitment of research staff and technical or research management staff under Chapter VI of the University's budget, as well as the selection processes of candidates, with the aim of progressively incorporating the CoARA principles.	2026-2027	VR Science Policy and Research.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Commission of Inquiry.	Updated regulations. Percentage of recruitment proposals from Chapter VI of the University's budget with the selection process adapted to the CoARA principles.
		Review and update, where appropriate, the selection process for competitions for the recruitment of trainee research staff, adjunct lecturers, substitute lecturers and labour research teaching staff under Chapter I of the University's budget, with the aim of progressively incorporating the CoARA principles.	2026-2027	VR Teaching and Research Staff	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Departments. Board of Directors. Governing Council.	Minutes of meetings with departments. Percentage of recruitment proposals from Chapter I of the University's budget with the selection process adapted to the CoARA principles.
		To review and update, where appropriate, the procedures and criteria for competitions for civil servant teaching and research staff, with the aim of progressively incorporating the CoARA principles.	2026-2027	VR Teaching and Research Staff	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Departments. Board of Directors.	Minutes of meetings with departments. Percentage of competitions with the selection process adapted to the CoARA principles.

					Governing Council.	
		To draw up regulations for the evaluation of the research activity of R+D+I structures based on the CoARA principles.	2Q 2026	VR Science Policy and Research	Commission of Inquiry.	Published Regulations.
		Define internal prioritisation mechanisms for the proposal of candidates within the framework of external calls (ATRAE, Consolidation, etc.), based on the CoARA principles.	2Q 2026	VR Science Policy and Research.	Commission of Inquiry.	Publication of the prioritisation criteria. Percentage of external calls with established prioritisation mechanisms.
		To review and update, where appropriate, the regulations for doctoral programmes and awards and competitions for doctoral students, with the aim of progressively incorporating the CoARA principles.	3Q 2026	Direction of the Doctoral School.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. VR in Postgraduate Planning and Policy and Lifelong Learning. Doctoral School	Updated regulations. Percentage of calls and awards incorporating CoARA criteria.
7. Raise awareness about the reform of research evaluation and provide transparent communication, guidance and training on the new	Internal strategy for communication, guidance and training on the CoARA principles and the reform of research evaluation at the UIB.	Organize a conference by specialists in research evaluation in accordance with the CoARA principles and good practices.	2026	Directorate of the Research Area.	Continuous Training of Teaching and Research. Research Services Unit of the Library, Documentation and Archive Area.	Percentage of participation. Satisfaction surveys.

criteria and processes, as well as on their use.		To organise annual training activities aimed at teaching and research staff, research management staff, members of evaluation committees, doctoral students and Library staff.	2026-2027	Research Services Unit of the Library, Documentation and Archive Area.	Continuous Training of Teaching and Research. Research Area. Doctoral School. Management.	Number of training activities organised. Percentage of participation. Satisfaction surveys.
	Preparation of support material.	Publication of short guides and frequently asked questions (FAQs).	3Q 2026	Research Services Unit of the Library, Documentation and Archive Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Communication Service.	Number of materials published. Number of downloads. Number of visits to FAQs.
		Definition of report templates for evaluation and selection committees, in accordance with the established CoARA criteria.	3Q 2026	Research Area Management	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Research Evaluation Committee of the Research Area. Departments.	Number of templates made.
		Preparation of a guide aimed at research staff for the preparation of narrative CVs.	2Q 2026	Research Services Unit of the Library, Documentation and Archive Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group.	Publication of the guide. Number of downloads.

8. Exchange practices and experiences with other institutions to promote mutual learning inside and outside the Coalition.	Exchange of information with CoARA and between the institutions participating in the Coalition.	Participation in the General Assembly of CoARA, in the Spanish National Chapter and in the working groups of strategic interest for the UIB.	2026-2027	VR Science Policy and Research	CoARA-UIB Working Group.	Incorporation of the activities of exchange of practices and experiences carried out in the reports of the CoARA-UIB Action Plan.
9. Communicate the progress made in the implementation of the commitments, facilitating self-evaluation and collective monitoring.	Internal strategic communication on the implementation of the actions of the CoARA-UIB Action Plan.	Preparation and execution of an internal communication plan on the changes introduced at the UIB for the reform of research evaluation.	2026-2027	VR Strategic Planning, Equality and Communication.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. Communication Service. Institutional Identity and Culture Service	Publication of the communication plan. Number of communication actions. Number of interactions on social networks.
		Creation and maintenance of the CoARA-UIB website and publication of information on the progress made in the implementation of the CoARA-UIB Action Plan (documentation, monitoring reports, calendar of activities, guides, support material and FAQs), as well as general information on CoARA and the reform of research evaluation at national and European level.	2026-2027	Directorate of the Research Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group. ICT Applications and Services Service. Communication Service.	Website creation. Periodic updating of the website. Number of visits to the website.
		Creation of a corporate email account.	2Q 2026	Directorate of the Research Area.	CoARA-UIB Working Group.	Creation of the email account.

					ICT Applications and Services Service.	
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, ensuring that the data used are available in open access to the research community.	Analyse and monitor actions that can be improved.	Annually review criteria, tools and processes in the light of the evidence and adjust the Action Plan.	2026-2027	VR Science Policy and Research.	CoARA-UIB Working Group.	Incorporation of proposals for improvement in the monitoring reports.